

KOKON-BUKHARA RELATIONS

Iskandarov Sultonbek Mavlon o'g'li

Student of the National University of Uzbekistan
named after Mirzo Ulugbek

Phone: +998975353305

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Abstract: This article describes the various conflicts between the Kokand Khanate and Bukhara, which took place after independence, and the disputes between these countries over various territories.

keywords: Oratepa, Okmachit, Tashkent, Shymkent, East Turkistan, Karategin, Kolob, Darvaz, Vahon, Muhammad Alikhan, Amir Nasrullo, Kasimov, Umarkhan.

The Khanate of Kokan, which separated from Bukhara, managed to strengthen its independence and expand its borders until the beginning of the 19th century. By the beginning of the 19th century, the process of centralization in the khanate intensified. Olim Khan (1798-1810) first managed to unite Ferghana, then Tashkent and Shymkent under his control. After Olim Khan, during the period of Umar Khan (1810-1822), the lands up to Issyk-Kul, Ili Valley and the Kazakh steppes at the foot of the Syr Darya were also subordinated to the Koqan Khanate. Okmachit fortress was built in the area connecting Bukhara, Khiva and Tashkent. It is difficult to say that Umar Khan maintained good neighborly relations with the emir of Bukhara. Although he had formed an alliance with Amir Haydar, the emir of Bukhara, in 1815 he marched to Turkestan, which belonged to Bukhara. The main reason for the start of the war was the possession of trade routes to Russia. In 1817, an uprising against the khanate broke out in Oratepa. Khan's troops suppressed the rebellion, albeit with great difficulty. Several rebels were executed by order of Umar Khan. In 1821, the Kazakh uprising began. The rebels temporarily occupied Sayram and Shymkent. Umar Khan, who succeeded in strengthening and expanding the state borders, died of illness in 1822. After his death, his 12-year-old (in some sources 15-year-old) son Muhammad Alikhan (Madalikhan) sat on the throne of Kokan. As a result of this, opposition against the khan arose. In 1826-1832, Madali Khan waged a war against the Chinese Empire in Eastern Turkestan. The reason for this is the incident of the Chinese government in the East. In Turkestan, there was pressure on the Khojas and Muslims. Muhammad Ali Khan's campaigns for the protection of Muslims in Eastern Turkestan did not go unnoticed by the emir of Bukhara. According to V. Nalivkin, in 1826, Amir Haidar sent an ambassador headed by Ismatullabi to the Khan with gifts and greetings. Muhammad Ali Khan planned to conquer the mountainous Tajik lands after his successes in Eastern Turkestan. By 1834, he subdued the regions of Korategin, Kolob, and Daroz, and sent troops to the regions of Vahon, Shugan, and Roshan. It is known that these lands belonged to the Bukhara Emirate or were dependent on it. Y. Kasimov stated that in 1745-1746, after the attack of the Kalmyk on the Fergana Valley and the victory of the Kokan over the Kalmyks, the Bukhara Khanate Kokan was forced to recognize the khanate as an independent state. Even so, the attitude of Bukhara towards the Kokan Khanate did not improve. Kokan Khan's march to Karategin, Kolob, Darvaz, Vahon, Shugnan, Roshan regions,

and his claim to the lands of Oratepa and Jizzakh further complicated the relationship. although he achieved a number of successes in politics, the movement of groups dissatisfied with the Khan did not decrease in the Kokan Khanate. Discontent in the occupied territories, ethnic diversity in the khanate contributed to the confusion of the issue.¹

With the arrival of Emir Nasrullah Khan (1826-1860) to the throne of Bukhara, Bukhara-Kokan relations became more tense. According to V. Nalivkin, Umar Khan, one of Nasrullah Khan's close relatives, fled from the emir's pressure and came to Kokan. He was very well received by the officials of Kokan. They even married him to the daughter of one of the Khan's close officials - Ishaq Devonbegi. Nasrullah Khan, in his turn, began to gather people who were dissatisfied with Madali Khan to Bukhara. Sultan Mahmud, Madal Khan's brother, who was expelled from Kokhan, also took refuge in the palace of the emir. According to the historical literature, he was appointed governor of Ormiton by order of the emir. The marriage of Madali Khan's late father's wife, i.e., stepmother Khanposhsha, who received the title of goose in the fight against the Ghairidins, was not only in the palace, but in the whole lowered his reputation in the khanate. The socio-political situation in the country has worsened. The incident of Khanposhshaoyim could come in very handy for Nasrullah Khan, who was waiting for a favorable moment to march to Kokan.Y. According to Kasimov, in 1840 (in some literature it is written that these events took place in 1842), Madali Khan wrote a letter about the violation of sharia laws by the opposition forces in the palace under the leadership of Kokanda Khan, and asked Nasrullah Khan for help (supposedly) to restore sharia laws. they say. Nasrullah Khan sent a letter to Madali Khan through his ambassadors, accusing and insulting him of marrying his stepmother. After that, Madali Khan started marching to Bukhara. The first battle between the troops of Kokand and Bukhara took place in August 1840 in Peshagar fortress near the border. According to Y. Kasimov, Peshagar belonged to Bukhara, where 800 soldiers of Amim were on defense. The soldiers of Bukhara suddenly attacked and hit the khan when Madali Khan was out for a walk with his 400 soldiers. Madalikhan barely managed to escape from the siege. Historical sources also give different information about this battle. For example, V. Nalivkin wrote that Peshagar was a stronghold of the Kokand Khanate and that Madali Khan entrusted the defense of the fortress to 1000 defenders led by Gadoibii Dodkhoh. when the shins attacked the fortress with an army of several thousand people, Gadoibii defeated the Bukhara vanguard. But, unable to withstand the next day's attack, he was forced to leave Peshagar.²

Taking advantage of the confusion in the Kokan army, a part of Amir Nasrullah Khan's soldiers marched to Khojand under the leadership of Sultan Mahmud, but the city surrendered without a fight. The armies of Sultan Mahmud and Nasrullah Khan united in Khojand and began to prepare for the conquest of Tashkent, but this time their battle plan did not come true: the officials of Tashkent wanted to go to Bukhara. The Bukhara troops, who won easily, soon after Tashkent, Konibodom, Mahram, Beshariq, and 30 from the city of Koqan who camped at a distance of a mile.³

¹ Ikromjon Kuzikov, "History of the Kokan Khanate", pp. 39-47. Namangan publishing house, 2014

² Bababekov Kh. Narodnye dvizheniya v Kokandskom khanstve i ix sotsialno-ekonomicheskie i politicheskie predposylki (XVIII-XIX vv.). - Tashkent: Science, 1990.

³ Bobobekov X- History of Kukon. - Tashkent: Science, 1996

Nasrullah Khan thought that the city of Kokan would be surrendered without a fight. However, the Kokanites have gathered all their military forces to the outskirts of the city to prepare for the defense of the city. The situation did not turn out as the emir expected: the war was prolonged. Due to the approach of winter, the shortage of food and clothing in the Bukhara army became worse. Since the main part of the army was made up of farmers, the grief of collecting the harvest from their land prevailed over fighting, and the army began to feel discontent. Under such conditions, making peace was the best way for Nasrullah Khan. He agreed to the agreement because Madal Khan's condition was not better than that of Nasrullah Khan. A peace treaty was concluded between the amir and the khan, and according to the agreement, the captured lands of Oratepa, Tashkent, Zomin, Ioma and Kan were recognized as belonging to Bukhara. Khojand and its surrounding lands were recognized as a separate independent state. Sultan Mahmud was declared the ruler of the new state (according to some reports, Madali Khan abdicated in favor of his brother). According to Amir Nasrullah Khan's plan, Khojand should be under the control of Bukhara. Amir Nasrullah Khan was convinced of the solidity of the eastern borders and returned to Bukhara. Both the lower class and the courtiers resented the heavy losses in the war. Sultan Mahmud, the ruler of the new Khojand state, did not want to recognize the authority of his brother. He took measures to strengthen the state. He even sent an ambassador to St. Petersburg and Governor-General of Siberia Gorchakov, expressing his sympathy for the development of Russia-Kokan (new Kokan) relations.⁴

Kokan khanate was attacked several times by Bukhara and after some time gained its independence, and Khan lands were recognized as belonging to Bukhara. Khojand and its surrounding lands were recognized as a separate independent state. Sultan Mahmud was declared the ruler of the new state (according to some reports, Madali Khan abdicated in favor of his brother). According to Amir Nasrullah Khan's plan, Khojand will be under the control of Bukhara needed. Amir Nasrullah Khan was convinced of the solidity of the eastern border and returned to Bukhara. Both the lower class and the courtiers resented the heavy losses in the war. Sultan Mahmud, the ruler of the new Khojand state, did not want to recognize the authority of his brother. He took measures to strengthen the state. He even sent an ambassador to St. Petersburg and Governor-General of Siberia Gorchakov, expressing his sympathy for the development of Russia-Kokan (new Kokan) relations.

In short, the Kokand Khanate completely recovered after its separation from the Bukhara Khanate, but after being hit by various blows from the Bukhara emirs, it became much weaker, but won a complete victory over the Bukhara emirs. Such wars in the country Although the trade relations between the khanate and the Bukhara Emirate were well preserved.

⁴ Kuldashev Sh. T. Political, economic and cultural ties between the Kokand Khanate and East Turkestan (XVIII - mid-XIX centuries). Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of candidate of historical sciences. - Tashkent, 2009.

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